

The following is a short description of places I have either seen, or heard of. It is regretted that owing to the absence of my Notes which are at present not available, I am not in a position to add more to these, nor am I in a position to describe those I have mentioned in a more elaborate and accurate way. I hope, however, if not all, at least a few of the places mentioned below will be of interest to you:-

1. In the vicinity of Sang-i-Safid village of Rudbar District carved and dressed stones resembling stone-arms are found in the debris of the ruins.
2. There are some old ruined bridges and caves along and about the river in Tang-i-Rudan (Bashgird District) respectively.
3. Qaleh Duzdghah (Bashgird District or nearby) is a natural hill-fort of past; ruins of ancient time buildings can still be seen there.
4. Chahar Gumbad (Sirjan &/or Afshar District) is situated south of Kuh-i-Bidakan where one will come across ruins of an ancient city. The ruins are almost covered with alluvium and only a searching eye with the aid of the still existing domes here and there can spot out the place.

Said-Abad-i-Sirjan

5. Another Qaleh east of ~~Said-i-Sirjan~~ on the way to Baft exists; remains of an old city-fort are still visible. Place is known by Said Abadis. Certain metal coins collected from these may be obtained from the villagers nearby.
6. Three miles south of Seh Chah which is situated on the western side of the main road to Bandar Abbas between Baft and Doultabad, there exist certain large dressed stones on a mountain which are believed to be very old Tomb-stones on graves of a renowned king and his family. The surrounding alluvium covered mounds of this place are believed to be the place of an ancient city, from the ruins of which a metal hat - helmet - (Kulah Khud) was found by one of the villagers there while digging.
7. Around the village Khabr and Khabr mountain, nearly 30 miles south of Baft, ruins of once famous towns are in existence, and in certain Tangs of the mountains large caves and wells can be seen which, it is said, were exploratory holes dug to find gold or platinum in the olden times. All along the lower part of the Southern slope of the Kuh-i-Khabr, a number of small domes within a short distance from one another are in existence. The villagers call them Khaneh Gouris (The House of Gabrs "Parsis"). These domes have a small entrance, only as big as to allow a man to crawl through. The top is opened by about a square foot. They are about six feet high and are stone-built. A series of similar domes exist at

the foot and southern side of the range of mountain stretching from north of Haji Abad towards Pur which is the boundary between the Sabah tribe of Fars and Afshar tribe of Kerman Province respectively. Also on the same mountain overhanging Hajiabad there are ruins of a tower. The belief is that this was the place where Noah's boat stood.

8. In the valleys between Kuh-i-Khabr and Siah Kuh there are two places, one near a cave which is said to have been a Truquoise mine, the other called Ghar-i-Maedan is near a big cave, and supposed to have been the place of mines for iron and other metals. There are ruins of ancient buildings and kilns. The whole area is said to be an ancient mining field.

LARISTAN VICINITY UP TO BANDAR TAHIRI.

9. In the two villages situated to the East and south of Lar which are both called Hormuz there are some natural hills and remains of ancient canals. Some of the inhabitants believe that either of the one or both the places had been the favourite place of Hormuz Shah at the time when it had a lot of gardens, while the others believe that they had been the places of the Fir-worshippers.

10. Qaleh Cirash is also said to be an ancient fort which had served as a strong lock up for Government prisoners during the reign of one of the Persian kings. It is

11. In Johan-Giran district about seven miles west of Bastakand in the valley near where Setwat-ul-Mamalik s/o late Mohammed Taqi Khan-i-Qawam resides, there are certain artificial caves at the southern foot of Kuh-i-Gabus which had been, it is said, made for prisoners in the ancient times, but some people describe them as Kharuf-Khanas i.e. the place where in olden days the old and feeble people who were unable to walk, hear or speak were being kept for the rest of their life time.

12. Khunj is situated west of Lar. Around this place there are many ruins consisting of ruins of domes minarets, etc. Hafez the well-known poet comes from this place. It is said to have been an important schooling place at one time.

13. At Ishkanan there is a history that the Qaleh Ishkanan, which had been the dwelling place of certain heroes in olden times, having been rebuilt by Baqir Khan had lost its antiquity. Another ruined fort is said to be in existence on the highest part of the range of Shiskuh which once served to control the road between this and the Gulf ports.

14. The whole area at Tombi situated near Gavbandi consists of domy Mounds as if they are natural ones, but around this place foundations of an old wall of a town are /

caravan due west of LAR.

are seen here and there. Filled up old canals and deep wells also can be seen. The inhabitants are of the idea that there had been an old town in days gone by which was ruined by Arabs when capturing Persia. With the exception of old eastern potteries no other antiquities were found there.

15. In the vicinity of Barrack, a village situated on the Gulf shore between Bandar Asalco and Teheri, one can find pieces of broken earthenware and a few small muddy mounds; these were once the place of ruins kilns.

BETWEEN BANDAR TAHERI, FIRUZABAD,
KAZERUN AND BUSHIRE.

16. In a Tang, situated on the main road from Bandar Taheri to Jam, foundations of an old metalled road and ruined water reservoir are seen here and there.

17. Qaleh Jam - Around this fort there are many ruins. On the top of the hill-like mound, which bears the name of Qaleh Jam, there are broken stone-walls which represent the ruins of its fortifications. The people have an idea that Jamshed Shah had built that Fort. Broken metal arrows are always found in the debris here.

18. Some 8 miles north of Hngam in Garmisiri Qashqai at the southern foot of Kuh-i-Surb there are many ruined and old kilns and pieces of melted metal of different shapes, also debris of ruined buildings within a distance of a few miles. It is said that there had not only been

a mining place but also factories of metal works existed. Lead is still being locally obtained for shotguns by the tribes.

19. Qaleh Parian, the mound on which Qaleh Parian is built is situated in Dasht-i-Kazrn. Around this fort the ruins are nearly covered with alluvium. The fort having been rebuilt by Soulat-i-Doulah has lost its antiquity. The people think that it had been once one of the seats of Changiz Khan. Gold coins and other antiquities of past are said to have been found from these ruins by Soulat-i-Doulat.

20. Firuzabad is also very famous for its ruins.

21. Between Farrashbadn and Noujain as well as in Hussain Abad plain there are many signs of ruins. The ruined walls of ancient artificial gardens here are very interesting. On the top of the mountain immediately north of the villages, there are a number of holes of unknown depth which always produce a sort of gurgling noise, the mystery of which nobody seems to know.

22. Kazerun, Tang-i-Shapur is sufficiently known by everybody for its relics.

23. The ruined fort of Qaleh Dokhtar at Kuh-i-Mund near Bandar Lavar and the remains of the ruined embankment and dams in its vicinity should also be interesting.

PARAS NOS. 1,2,3,4,10 are places not seen by me personally.

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PARAS NOS. 5,6,9,21 & Hajiabad in Para 7 are places
reachable by car.

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M-I-S., 20th Oct., 1932.